

INTERACTIVE TECHNOLOGIES - AN IMPORTANT TOOL FOR DEVELOPING THE LOGICAL THINKING OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Annotation: Interactive educational method is implemented by each teacher at the level of available tools and capabilities. In this, each student learns at different levels according to his motives and intellectual level. The use of interactive methods helps to increase the effectiveness of the lesson. This article describes in detail that interactive technologies are an important tool for developing the logical thinking of elementary school students.

Keywords: interlaol methods of education, advanced pedagogical technologies, educational process, development of modern education system, cooperation between teacher and student, logical thinking, innovative approach.

Today, in a number of developed countries, the methods that form the basis of great experience in the use of modern pedagogical technologies that guarantee the effectiveness of the educational process are called interactive methods. Interactive educational methods are currently the most common and widely used methods in all types of educational institutions. At the same time, there are many types of interactive educational methods, and there are currently suitable ones for the implementation of almost all tasks of the educational process. In practice, it is possible to select the ones that are suitable for specific purposes and use them accordingly. This situation has created the problem of choosing the right interactive educational methods to achieve certain goals.

For this purpose, the lesson process should be organized rationally, the teacher should increase the interest of the learners and constantly encourage their activity in the educational process, divide the educational material into small parts,

and open their content intellectually. it is required to use methods such as attack, small group work, debate, problem situation, guided text, project, role play and encourage learners to do practical exercises independently.

The interactive method is to solve an activity or problem in a mutual dialogue, in the course of thinking in a mutual debate, with unity. The advantage of this method is that the entire activity teaches the student to think independently and prepares him for an independent life.

When choosing interactive methods of teaching, the purpose of education, the number and capabilities of learners, the educational and material conditions of the educational institution, the duration of education, the pedagogical skills of the teacher, etc. are taken into account.

Interactive methods mean methods that activate learners and encourage them to think independently, with the learner at the center of the educational process. When these methods are used, the teacher invites the learner to actively participate. The learner is involved throughout the process. The benefits of a learner-centered approach include:

- reading and learning with a higher educational effect;
- high motivation of the learner;
- consideration of previously acquired knowledge;
- aligning the educational process with the goals and needs of the learner;
- support of the learner's initiative and responsibility;
- learning by doing;
- creation of conditions for two-way feedback.

It is clear from the above that it is necessary to properly analyze the interactive educational methods and classify them on this basis. Below we present general comments on this issue. When classifying these methods, they can be divided into interactive methods, interactive educational strategies, and interactive graphic organizers.

Currently, the most popular interactive educational methods are:

1. Interactive methods: "Case-study" (or "Educational cases"), "Blist survey", "Modeling", "Creative work", "Problematic education" and others.

2. Interactive educational strategies. When distinguishing interactive educational strategies from the composition of interactive educational methods, the approach to organizing group work is based on the fact that, in a certain sense, it is compared to strategic planning. In fact, these strategies are more related to interactive educational methods, and there are no other differences between them.

3. Interactive graphic organizers: "Fish skeleton", "BBB", "Conceptual table", "Venn diagram", "T-table", "Insert", "Cluster", "Why?", "How?" and b. The separation of interactive graphic organizers is based on the fact that the main ideas are expressed in written form in various graphic forms. In fact, working with these graphic organizers is more related to interactive educational methods, and there are no other differences between them.

Interactive educational methods are often used simultaneously with various forms of training technologies. The use of these methods increases the activity of training participants and improves the effectiveness of education. The use of interactive methods and educational games, modern information and communication technologies in elementary grades helps students to think independently, expand the scope of creative research and logical thinking, and connect what they learned in classes with life, and increase their interest. . The effective use of the conditions created by teachers based on such modern requirements and the organization of classes based on advanced pedagogical and information communication technologies guarantees the quality of the educational process.

In our opinion, the main requirements for educational games are as follows:

1. Educational games should be suitable for the age of students;
2. The games should be proportionate to the content of the topic being played;
3. The time of educational games must be clearly defined;
4. Educational games should have both educational and educational value;

5. The purpose and significance of educational games should be defined.

Only when the above requirements are followed, the effectiveness of the lesson increases and modern technologies serve the effectiveness of education.

The interactive method is an important means of solving an activity or problem in a mutual dialogue, in the course of thinking in a mutual debate. The advantage of this method is that the entire activity teaches the student to think independently and prepares him for an independent life. The use of interactive methods in the process of teaching subjects has its own characteristics. Careful study and practical application of each interactive method used in educational practice expands the thinking of students and has a positive effect on finding the right solution to the problem. It increases the creativity and activity of students. It should not be forgotten that the analysis of various theoretical and practical problems through interactive methods is an important tool for expanding and deepening the knowledge, skills, and abilities of students.

In conclusion, it can be said that if classes in primary classes are organized on the basis of modern educational technologies, as a result, fear, stuttering, mistrust will disappear, a situation of equality, freedom, and self-confidence will be born for the student. By creating conditions for the student to develop his strength and potential, the undiscovered aspects are opened, and his passion and pleasure for reading increases. Even if small, every step taken by the student towards progress is considered an achievement, it leads the student to innovation, has a positive effect on his ability to think independently, his activity, interest in learning, increases responsibility. That is how our main goal - solid and thorough assimilation of knowledge is achieved, the effectiveness of the lesson is guaranteed.

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